

Accessibility, Usability and Satisfaction of Library Users in the Hybrid Resources and Services of Academic Libraries in the Province of Albay

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Abstract:- This study determines the Accessibility, usability and satisfaction of library users in the hybrid resources and services of academic libraries in Albay province. The methodology used in this research was descriptive-correlational technique. As result in conducting the study the findings were as follows: 1. the level of accessibility of academic libraries in the Province of Albay was high with an average weighted mean of 3.27 accessible in terms of hybrid resources and services. 2. The level of usability for hybrid Resources and Services are both high with the weighted mean of 3.21. 3. The level of satisfaction of library users was high with an average weighted mean of 3.25., 4. There is a significant relationship between the level of accessibility and level of usability since the p value of 0.000 was lower than the level of significance at 0.01., 5. There is a significant relationship between the level of usability and satisfaction in the hybrid resources and services since the p value of 0.000 was lower than the level of significance at 0.01., 6. There is a significant relationship between the level of accessibility and satisfaction of the academic libraries in the province of Albay since the p value of 0.000 was lower than the level of significance at 0.01., 7. An action plan is designed to implicate in the result based on the findings of the study. The researcher has concluded after the result on the findings: 1. The library users are more often of accessing the hybrid resources than accessing its hybrid services. 2. The library users seldom utilize the hybrid services offered by the academic libraries. 3. Despite the low percentage in the accessibility and usability of hybrid resources, the library users still access and utilize both hybrid resources and services of academic libraries which lead to generate a highly satisfied level for satisfaction. 4. The higher the level of accessibility in academic libraries, the higher the level of usability of hybrid resources. 5. The higher level of accessibility of academic libraries, the higher level of usability of hybrid services. 6. The higher the level of accessibility and usability of the hybrid resources and services, the higher satisfaction will be rated from the library users. 7. An action plan is a tool in improving for the weak percentage on the hybrid library resources and services indicated for the accessibility and usability of users in the academic libraries of the Province of Albay.

I. INTRODUCTION

Science and technology, including libraries used as learning spaces for students, are improving significantly as a result of the digital revolution. The concept of the hybrid library is an extension of traditional libraries which use digital technology within the system (Lukman, 2021). It is a gateway of improving the access and utilization in such digital age where the gaps between the tradition and modernization of services and resources were being able to combine for a high satisfaction from the users. Significantly, hybrid resources and services are important in accessibility and usability of library users in academic libraries. It shall be regarded as a very valuable instrument in support of teaching, learning and research activities at the university that will provide users with general information resources and services (Anunobi and Okoye 2008). Presently, due to the existing crisis over pandemic of COVID19, the operation of all libraries including the academic library has been challenged as to how the researchers would access and utilize the resources and services now that we are in a global pandemic. In order to prevent the spread of this virus, which affects education systems and even libraries itself, governments around the world have placed their countries under complete or partial lockdown. A variety of learning methods, including ones that do not require more commonly available technologies or techniques, have been introduced by many governments around the world. The implication of this acquired strategy in the pursuit of education in part of libraries is as well to elevate in the provision of service, facilities and resources not only the academic libraries but as well as other types of libraries into a hybrid form.

As the Philippines is one of the countries which develops strategies to pursue the education system of the country, the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) created a mandate of flexible learning schemes among the students from academic institutions. Stated in CHED Memorandum Order n.4, series of 2020 which subject the guidelines on the implementation of the flexible learning scheme enclosed that the design and delivery of programs, courses and learning interventions address the learners' unique needs in terms of place, pace, process and products of learning which involves the use of both digital and non-digital technology and covers

both face-to-face, out-of-classroom learning modes of delivery or a combination of modes of deliver. Supporting this order, as part of the academic library strategy addressing the flexible learning; an official released memo for the guidelines on the recalibration of miscellaneous and other school fees (MOSF) during the COVID-19 dated March 24, 2021, announced the creation and / or expansion of e-library/digital library/online library as part of the scope of this memo. With the existing situation, the researcher has decided to conduct a study entitled *Accessibility, Usability and Users' Satisfaction in the Hybrid Resources and Services of the Academic Libraries in the Province of Albay* to look deeper whether the strategies being implies during this time of pandemic to the students and teachers are effective and efficient.

II. OPERATIONAL FRAMEWORK

From the theory of Penchansky it was noted that the access is defined in dimension of access, and one is accessibility. Access in form of accessibility as part of different dimensions are dependent yet interconnected with each other. While theoretical usability, access to human eye as user experience of technology and choosing the type of system that can make it most efficient and least burdensome are all part of this. These two theories directed the level of accessibility and usability in hybrid resources and services. While for the E. Deming's theory is significantly related in terms of transformation within the libraries in terms of hybrid resources and services determines the satisfaction level in accessibility and usability of library users. The operational model of the study presented the variables of the study, in which the level of accessibility and level of usability in the hybrid resources and services are the independent variables, while the level of satisfaction on the hybrid resources and services when correlates to the accessibility and usability is the dependent variable.

III. REVIEW ON LITERATURES AND STUDY

➤ *Accessibility And Usability*

Gunnore (2022) conducted a study on Accessible services in academic libraries: a content analysis of library accessibility webpages in the United States, findings revealed that Libraries have broadened and strengthened efforts to publicize/provide services and resources to functionally diverse users. Information about assistive technologies, services and equipment is the most commonly prioritized by these pages. These pages were different in size, complexity and detail, but there was greater coverage and information on public institutions' websites than private ones. For better communication to users, libraries can work on creating more accessible pages and increasing transparency and evidence of currency. Traditionally, libraries have been collections of books, manuscripts, journals and various sources for recording information. Newspapers and books, as well as other forms of written material, constitute a significant part of the Traditional Library Collection. Xem, (2021), he further stated that

libraries are the place to preserve and distribute the physical forms of resources, such as books and magazines, journals, periodicals.

The accessibility and usability of library websites for students with visual and physical disabilities in Kenya's public universities are examined in Kiruki, Beatrice Wamaitha's (2021) study. The study used a mixed-methods approach using a survey research design. Focus groups, structured interviews, survey questionnaires, and observation were used to collect the data. Six public colleges that have a history of accepting students with disabilities made up the study population. Students with visual disabilities (86), students with physical disabilities (91), university librarians (6), staff from disability mainstreaming departments (6), systems librarians (6), and library staff who provided information services to students with disabilities (133) made up the study sample that was compiled using the census. The IFLA Access to Libraries for Persons with Disabilities Checklist and the Social Model of Disability served as the study's conceptual and theoretical frameworks. According to the study's findings, every library has a website. However, neither the websites nor the information they included were tailored to people with impairments. Additionally, some students with disabilities were unaware that libraries had websites and that they offered online resources through them. The layout of the website also presented a number of accessibility issues. The investigation came to the conclusion that public university libraries' websites were inaccessible to and ineffective for use by people with impairments. The authors suggested that disability services pages with information tailored to people with disabilities be included on library websites. Additionally, libraries should assess their websites to make sure they meet W3C guidelines for accessible web content. Libraries should also create a disability policy to provide direction on how to provide information services to people with impairments.

A study on the usability and accessibility of academic libraries for students with impairments was undertaken by Schmetzke in 2021. According to the report, all library services, events, and activities must be accessible to people with disabilities under the Americans with Disabilities Act (ADA). Today's academic libraries are heavily reliant on web-based indexes and databases. This study intends to look into how these online resources are accessible and usable for people who use adaptive software to interact with computers. Database connections were assessed using two different approaches: By using minimally trained subjects to perform routine search-related tasks, the interfaces were tested for functionality when used in conjunction with adaptive software frequently used by people with print disabilities. Selected screens of the interfaces were checked for compliance with major Section 508 and web Content Accessibility Guidelines components. Based on document format, accessibility of content within documents was assessed. The usability data provided for each of the 37 evaluated databases assists librarians in making more informed purchasing decisions,

provides direction to companies wishing to design more inclusive products, and warns those who provide support to screen reader or audio browser users about potential challenges with particular library databases.

Akgul, (2020) claimed that the web is a crucial component of institutions of higher learning. Universities can reach their target audiences via their websites in an effective, efficient, and satisfactory manner, regardless of any handicap. Universities must make the appropriate design adjustments to ensure web content accessibility as the proportion of impaired students enrolled in higher education increases. In his report, he rates the readability, usability, performance quality, and accessibility of all Turkish official and private university websites. Most did not adhere to WCAG 2.0 accessibility standards. These results show low usability, quality performance, and readability, highlighting the need for Turkish universities to allocate more resources to making their websites more accessible, usable, high-quality performance, and readable for all of their potential users. Out of 110 state university websites and 69 private university websites, only 10 state and four private university websites attained conformance Level A.

According to Fonseca and Penalvo (2020), Usability and accessibility of educational data are even more important in light of the global pandemic caused by the COVID-19 disease-causing SARS-CoV-2 virus. The impact this crisis is having on schooling is unprecedented. 91.3% of all students enrolled globally were impacted by the epidemic in the first few months of 2020, according to UNESCO, and due to school and university closures, more than 1.5 billion people were unable to get face-to-face education. The effects are especially severe in developing nations and for families who are poor and at danger of exclusion. They also exhibit digital inequality and create exclusion and unequal conditions for weaker groups, such as women, people of color, and people with disabilities. The online transformation of educational activities, particularly evaluation procedures, has been noted to provide significant obstacles.

Therefore, it is crucial to increase accessibility to educational technologies and close usage and literacy disparities. Deploying technological ecosystems that support blended or online learning, teacher and student training for effective use of educational technologies, and policies for both governmental and academic leaders to define strategies and manage uncertain scenarios all require a multidisciplinary approach. Transparency, morality, and respect for individual rights must all be upheld in the context of educational data access.

According to the publication of ACER for Education ¹(2020), An open-shelf library is a place where users are free to interact with one another and with the items in the collection, handling and looking for their own books; in a closed-shelf library, only the employees have direct access to

the collection and the user's role is reduced to requesting specific titles that might or might not be permitted in any way to leave the building. The biggest difference isn't that the former is more secure against a pandemic; rather, it's the fundamental shift in how readers select books to read. A wide search is better suited to an open-shelf library because you can enter with only a vague idea of the subject or genre you're interested in and possibly leave with something unexpected. On the other hand, a closed-shelf library necessitates a focused method of searching where the user is expected to ask for certain titles.

➤ *Satisfaction*

At the Eastern University Library in Bangladesh, Alam (2021) conducted a research to assess the impact of SERVQUAL aspects on user satisfaction. Results showed that the regression model described the 56.9% variation in user satisfaction and was verified as significant ($p < 0.001$). The findings suggested that user satisfaction was highly influenced by the library's resources ($p < 0.004$), staff responsiveness ($p < 0.001$), and tangible amenities ($p < 0.001$).

Gyau (2021) claimed that measuring user happiness is an important factor in determining how well a library performs in terms of providing high-quality services, and it can help libraries identify areas for innovation. The study's primary objective is to assess student opinions on user satisfaction with academic library services in order to compare that to overall library service quality.

The results of the Kwakye (2021) study show that patrons are happy with the library's assistance with learning and research, and patron and student treatment of patrons and students assessed the library's overall service quality as good. The results demonstrate that there is a positive and significant relationship between user satisfaction and the overall quality of library services. Pearson correlation analysis and multivariate analysis of variance (one-way MANOVA) were used to measure these relationships and effects. Few customers are unhappy with the academic library's support for study and research, as well as the way the library treats its patrons, so the academic still has to improve its services. The study's findings will help academic libraries create strategies that will better ensure that consumers receive high-quality services, increase their happiness, and draw in new customers. Additionally, this would make it easier for academic libraries to evaluate customer happiness and opinions on services on a regular basis.

Veeramallu (2021) examines users' perceptions and levels of satisfaction with engineering college libraries' information resources. The results showed that the majority of respondents rated their satisfaction with libraries and information resources as high yet the majority did not use them. Similar to this, Liu (2021) found that one of the key factors affecting how well academic libraries do in providing excellent service to customers is user happiness. The main

goal of all academic libraries is to provide high-quality services that meet the needs of all of their users, including teachers/lecturers, students, and library staff, in order to support them in their roles as teachers, learners, and researchers in order to advance the library, the university, and the country as a whole. Therefore, it is imperative for academic libraries, which are the driving force behind the learning and research processes at universities, to meet the demands of their customers by providing excellent services and also by regularly conducting user surveys to collect opinions and gauge satisfaction with the services in order to further develop them.

Hani (2021) noted that modern virtual libraries were in the forefront of international efforts to preserve documentary legacy in her paper released online for Digital Libraries to Ease Learning in the Philippines. They are in a particularly advantageous position to promote and actively participate in digital conservation. The COVID-19 problem has acted as a turning point, bringing to light all of the benefits that digital libraries offer. In fact, digital libraries have shown that they have the power to not only permit a richer, more varied public domain, but also to advance human growth in general. She added that it is probable that e-library usage will keep expanding exponentially in the future. This innovation will be propelled by current demands and worldwide trends including the explosive growth of smartphones, the surge in ICT-based reading devices, and the now-ingrained habit of looking for information online.

Schools have been suspended in many nations throughout the world, and many teachers and parents are concerned about how to continue the school year both during and after the suspension, this was mentioned in a vlog (2020) about Free Online Libraries During COVID-19. Numerous online libraries and sites have offered up their databases for free in response. The National Library of the Philippines was the first library in the Philippines to offer free databases of library resources, and it is available to anybody who emails in a request.

In order to determine the impact of information resources' accessibility and availability on user satisfaction, Onwukanjo (2017)'s study focused only on undergraduate students at the Federal University of Technology Minna. The study's main goals were to determine whether users were satisfied with the library's resources, to identify the information resources that are available in the FUTMinna library, to determine whether the resources are current, relevant, and sufficient, to determine whether the resources are accessible to users, and to determine any difficulties that users may have having access to the information resources. The survey research design was used, and the instrument for gathering data was a questionnaire. Using a basic random sampling procedure, a sampling fraction of 2.2% was used to choose 376 students from the entire population of 19,090. Two hypotheses were evaluated at the 0.05 level of significance, and the data was given in frequency, tables, and percentages.

The T-test method was used to assess the hypotheses. The study's findings show low user satisfaction, inadequate and outdated information resources, a lack of services for current awareness, printing and copying, and subpar and dysfunctional information retrieval tools. The study came to the conclusion that no library can be self-sufficient in meeting users' demands and that the inadequate and out-of-date nature of the information resources supplied has either directly or indirectly contributed to low user satisfaction. According to the study, in order to improve the low level of user satisfaction, current and adequate information resources should be acquired. Additionally, librarians should make use of their expertise in media librarianship, reference and bibliography, and organization of knowledge one and two to make sure that users have access to efficient information retrieval tools and audio-visual resources that will support interactive learning.

In his essay, Tiemo (2016) stated that users' pleasure may be viewed as the satisfaction they experience after using the library's numerous informational resources and services to meet their informational demands for a variety of everyday activities. As a result, the availability of top-notch informational resources and services in libraries does have a big impact on how satisfied users are. When users are happy with the information resources available at the library, they not only return but also recommend the library to other users.

A library's contribution to a learning community is fundamental to a student's academic growth, thus it must provide modern services that are essential in the age of computers. According to De Grandbois (2016), service entails the use of knowledge, abilities, and skills by one individual or organization for the benefit of another. Information is delivered to library users through services. For the goal of identifying gaps and improving services and information delivery strategies based on patron wants and requests, it is crucial to review library services. She continued further stating that the convenience of a library web portal is one of the modern library services generated by the wave of ICT. Patrons of libraries use the facilities, equipment, and collection of the libraries. Through a library portal, all of these library functions may be accessed remotely. To better serve their customers, many libraries currently provide a library online site. Libraries would wish to assist their customers and offer library services everywhere and at any time. As it is their world today, this technique has a lot to offer library users. As a result, libraries must change and respond to the sophisticated information requirements of their patrons as well as technological advancements.

Gohain (2013) in his study looked at how Tezpur University students and research researchers used the library's resources, how satisfied they were with those resources and services, and how they went about finding information. To gather pertinent information, 200 questionnaires were given to Tezpur University students and researchers. 32.07% (51) of respondents visited the Central Library at Tezpur University

every day to borrow books, according to a survey of 79.5% (159) library users. In order to satisfy their information demands, it was discovered that 82.39% (131) of users borrowed textbooks, (79.87%) (127) examined journals, and (75.47%) (120) read newspapers. In order to satisfy the diverse informational needs of students and researchers, libraries play a crucial role. It is felt that user guidance is necessary to help library users to meet their information needs and make users aware of the available library resources and services.

➤ *Research Design*

In order to gather data and provide insights, this study used a descriptive-correlational technique of research to assess the usability, accessibility, and user satisfaction of the hybrid services and resources offered by the university libraries in Albay. According to (McCombes, 2019), descriptive research tries to precisely and methodically characterize a population, situation, or phenomena. It can respond to inquiries about what, where, when, and how. A descriptive research strategy can study one or more variables using a wide range of research techniques. Its objective is to notice and record specifics of a situation as they emerge spontaneously, and occasionally it also serves as a springboard for developing theories or hypotheses.

IV. SUMMARY OF FINDINGS, CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study determines the accessibility, usability and satisfaction of library users of academic libraries within province of Albay. It primarily aimed to respond to the following: 1. Accessibility level of academic libraries within Albay province along; hybrid resources; and hybrid services? 2. Usability level of academic libraries in Albay province in terms of; 2.1 hybrid resources; and 2.2 hybrid services? 3. Satisfaction levels of academic libraries in Albay province in terms of; 3.1 hybrid resources; and 3.2 hybrid services? 4. Significant relationship between the accessibility level and usability level of academic libraries' hybrid services and resources in Albay province? 5. Significant relationship between the Usability level and satisfaction level of academic libraries in the hybrid resources and services within Albay province.? 6. Significant relationship between the accessibility level and satisfaction level in hybrid resources and services of academic libraries in Albay province?

The study employed descriptive-correlational method of research to ascertain facts and generate insights on the accessibility, usability and satisfaction of library users in the academic libraries in the Province of Albay. The method was utilized and tested the null of hypothesis that Ho1. There was a significant relationship between the level of accessibility and usability in the hybrid resources and services of the academic libraries in the province of Albay, Ho2. There is significant relationship between the level of usability and satisfaction in the hybrid resources and services of the academic libraries in

the province of Albay, Ho3. There is significant relationship between the level of accessibility and satisfaction of the academic libraries in the province of Albay. The study was conducted to five selected academic schools and retrieved 200 responses from users out of 250 target respondents.

Quantifying the results on the level of accessibility, level of usability and satisfaction level on the hybrid academic libraries, the weighted mean was utilized in this study, while to check for the significant relationship between dependent variables, the Pearson r p- value was used.

➤ *Accessibility of the Academic Libraries in the Province of Albay in Hybrid Resources*

From the conducted survey, it revealed that physical books and references materials were the top accessible in their libraries. This implies that these two resources are very high in terms of accessibility, the results were supported by the article of Xem, (2021) which stated that traditionally, libraries were collections of books, manuscripts, journals, and other sources of recorded information. The majority of the materials in conventional libraries' collections are printed materials, manuscripts, etc. Libraries are places where tangible resources like books, magazines, journals, and periodicals are preserved and disseminated. Opara (2019) which he stated in his written work on hybrid libraries that libraries have traditionally existed to collect and organize information, make access knowledge more democratic, and preserve the record of ideas for future general libraries in the digital age which innovate technological developments to revolutionize information access and use.

➤ *Accessibility of the Academic Libraries in the Province of Albay in Hybrid Services*

Library Services was tested in a form of survey to determine the most accessible service in academic libraries within the province of Albay. In which, library hours followed by the Online and Physical Current Awareness Services got the highest rank in survey. According to Opara (2019), librarians and information professionals must be connected to the local communities they serve, provide services that are relevant to local needs, connect citizens to the world's knowledge, and create the last decade's explosion of technology into libraries has had an impact on not only library processes but more importantly, the minds and hearts of communities. To summarize the level of accessibility of academic libraries in the Province of Albay is highly accessible in terms of hybrid resources and services. Hence hybrid resources with rank 1 denoting that the resources in the academic libraries in both traditional and digital format is more accessible than the hybrid services. According to Allen (2021), a hybrid library is a setting with both physical and virtual services supporting users' professional activities in their place of employment, ranging from information discovery to resource manipulation and analysis.

➤ *Usability of the Academic Libraries in the Province of Albay: Hybrid Resources*

Libraries were collections of written materials including books, journals, and manuscripts. He also mentioned that libraries are the location to conserve and disseminate the tangible forms of materials, such as books and magazines, journals, periodicals, etc. The collection of traditional libraries is mostly comprised of print media, manuscripts, etc. Similar to this, academic libraries in the Province of Albay demonstrate that users continue to primarily use physical books, scoring well in the study.

➤ *Usability of the Academic Libraries in the Province of Albay: Hybrid Services*

Ogbonna (2014) defined hybrid libraries as those that combine conventional print resources with an increasing number of electronic-based ones. However, hybrid libraries have become the new standard in the majority of academic and public libraries in the industrialized world, and they are also being seriously explored in many academic libraries in developing nations, particularly Nigeria. He stated that hybrid libraries allow integrated resource discovery, whether those resources are in analog or digital format, local, national, or worldwide, and that they are more than just interfaces. Similar to this, the results of the study on the usability of academic libraries' hybrid services reveal that Library Hours is a more practical service for users, both in traditional and online service.

➤ *Summary on the Level of Usability of the Academic Libraries in the Province of Albay*

The level of usability for hybrid Resources and Services are both highly usable obtaining 3.21 in overall weighted mean. Hence, hybrid resources got the rank 1 which denotes that the resources in both digital and physical resources were highly usable than the hybrid services.

➤ *Satisfaction of the Academic Libraries in the Province of Albay*

The findings on the on the level of satisfaction of users for hybrid resources and services was revealed a high satisfaction with an average weighted mean of 3.22. Thus, the availability of quality information resources and services in libraries do have a significant influence on users' satisfaction. When users are satisfied with library information resources, they not only come back but speak well of the library to other users.

Moreover, the result is similarly connected with the study of Kwakye (2021) on results of the study which indicated that users are satisfied with both library's support for learning and research, and the library's treatment of users and students rated the overall quality of services provided by the library as good. The results demonstrate that there is a positive and significant relationship between user satisfaction and the overall quality of library services. Pearson correlation analysis and multivariate analysis of variance (one-way MANOVA)

were used to measure these relationships and effects. Few customers are unhappy with the academic library's assistance for study and research, as well as the way the library treats its patrons, so the academic still has to enhance its services.

The outcomes of the study will assist academic libraries to formulate effective strategies to ensure better delivery of quality services to the users to enhance their satisfaction, thereby attracting more users. This will also help academic libraries to regularly analyze user's satisfaction and their views on academic library services.

❖ *Findings*

The findings revealed as follows:

- The level of accessibility of academic libraries in the Province of Albay was high with an average weighted mean of 3.27 accessible in terms of hybrid resources and services.
- The level of usability for hybrid Resources and Services was both high with 3.21 weighted mean.
- The level of satisfaction of library users was high with an average weighted mean of 3.25.
- Since the p value of 0.000 was less than the level of significance at 0.01 there is a significant correlation between the degree of accessibility and level of usability.
- Since the p value of 0.000 was less than the level of significance at 0.01 there is a significant link between the degree of usability and satisfaction with the hybrid resources and services.
- Since the p value of 0.000 was less than the level of significance at 0.01 there is a significant correlation between the accessibility and satisfaction of academic libraries in the province of Albay.
- In accordance with the findings of the research, an action plan is created to as implication of the study.

❖ *Conclusion*

Based on the findings, this study has come up with the following conclusions.

- The library users are more often of accessing the hybrid resources than accessing its hybrid services.
- The library users seldom utilize the hybrid services offered by the academic libraries.
- Despite the low percentage in the accessibility and usability of hybrid resources, the library users still access and utilize both hybrid resources and services of academic libraries which lead to generate a highly satisfied level for satisfaction.
- The higher the level of accessibility in academic libraries, the higher the level of usability of hybrid resources.
- The higher level of accessibility of academic libraries, the higher level of usability of hybrid services.
- The higher the level of accessibility and usability of the hybrid resources and services, the higher satisfaction will be rated from the library users.

- An action plan is a tool in improving for the weak percentage on the hybrid library resources and services indicated for the accessibility and usability of users in the academic libraries of the Province of Albay.

❖ Recommendation

Recommendation was detailed below;

- There is a need of improvement on the accessibility of hybrid resources on E-books and STARbooks, as well as improvement on the accessibility of hybrid services in terms of Internet and Audio-Visual materials.
- There is a need of improvement on the usability of hybrid resources such as Starbooks and Audio-Visual materials specifically the PODCAST usage, while for the hybrid services the need of improvement in terms of Internet Access Services and Audio-Visual service is also recommended.
- There is a need of improvement on the hybrid services specifically on the Audio-visual resources such as PODCAST and CD ROMS in its accessibility and usability to gain a higher satisfaction rate from the library users.
- The higher level of library users in terms of accessing the library, the higher usability of hybrid resources. For this to maintain, there should be a concrete plan on sustaining and upgrading the offered resources in both digital and physical format.
- The higher level of library users in terms accessibility of library, the higher usability of hybrid services. For the effectivity/ efficiency of hybrid services in both digital and manual form there is a need of suggestion box / helpline service for the users to address where the offered services weaken.
- There should be an action plan addressed to the problems suggested by the library users upon creating the to accelerate the ratings on the accessibility and usability of hybrid services.
- The designed action plan may be suggested and endorsed to the academic libraries.

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